

THE USE OF AN INDUSTRIAL ROBOT FOR WINDING COMPLEX PARTS

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ABSTRACT

At the Department of Mechanical Engineering at K.U.Leuven, a filament winding unit has been constructed, consisting of a PUMA-762 robot and an external axis, on which the mandrel is mounted. The payout eye is mounted on the robot wrist and has an additional rotation possibility to enable winding with tapes. Out from a drawing of the part in a CAD-system, fibre paths are selected so that the part is as strong as possible. An off-line collision-free robot program is generated. The wound part is non-destructive tested with the robotic ultrasonic C-scan technique.

1 INTRODUCTION

Filament Winding is a production technique which can be automated strongly. A computer integrated method has been developed for the design, production and testing of filament wound parts.

The main problem in the design of a filament wound part is the selection of the fibre paths so that the wound part meets all the design requirements. The geometry of the part is defined in a commercial CAD/CAM system. Geodesical fibre paths are

calculated in an external program. Stress calculations are performed with a finite element program. To be able to analyze the stresses in a complex wound part, an interface-program has been developed to generate the laminate lay-up from the wound part out from the trajectories of the individual fibre paths.

Based on the data of the fibre paths the control data for the filament winding machine are calculated. In the department of Mechanical Engineering at the K.U.Leuven two filament winding machines have been developed : a small low-cost filament winding machine with two axes to wind axisymmetrical parts, and a robotic filament winding machine which is able to wind more complex parts, like T-connections.

The robot, which is used for winding, is also used for the non-destructive control of the wound part with the ultrasonic C-scan technique. The geometrical data of the CAD-model are used to generate the robot path.

2 DESIGN OF FILAMENT WOUND PARTS

2.1 Fibre Paths The design of a filament wound part is a compromise between, on the one hand, what is optimal according to stiffness and strength, and, on the other hand, the restrictions imposed by the winding process. The selection of the fibre paths, so that the part is as strong as possible, is the main problem in the design phase.

The most stringent condition is that the fibre path may not slip on the surface. The transverse force acting on the fibre should therefore be less than the friction between the fibre and the material underneath. When no friction is allowed at all, this condition results in the use of geodesic paths.

If, instead of single fibre bundles, tapes are used for winding all of the longitudinal fibres of the tape should have the same length. If the tape is small this requirement leads also to the use of geodesic paths.

Not every slip-free fibre path can be used for winding. When the part has locally concave parts, like a fillet between two surfaces, the fibre can lift off from the surface, taking a shorter way to the air. Fibre bridging will be a major criterion for rejecting a fibre path.

A computer program CAWAR (Computer Aided filament Winding of Asymmetric shapes using Robots) has been developed for the calculation of geodesical fibre paths on a part

composed out of several surfaces. The geometry of the part is described in a commercial CAD surface modeller. This CAD-model can be used for the fabrication of a base-mould on a CNC-machine. After the creation of the surface model, the geometrical data are made accessible for the program **CAWAR** by the creation of an IGES-file [1]. IGES is an international standardised format for interchanging data between CAD-systems. The calculation of the fibre path is based on solving the differential equation of the geodesic path. The mathematical parameters of the surfaces are extracted out of the IGES-file. In order to detect fibre bridging, the program checks the curvature of the path continuously.

To be able to calculate the stresses in the wound part, an interface program (**LUPGEN** [2]) has been written to calculate the lay-up of the wound part out from the trajectory of the individual fibre paths.

2.2 Design Methodology In order to provide a starting point for building up the winding laminate, stress calculations are performed on an isotropic model. Out from the calculated stresses, ideal fibre orientations are derived. Unfortunately, due to the restrictions imposed on the fibre paths, these ideal fibre angles can not always be achieved.

In the case of axisymmetric structures, a winding step can be defined by using the data of a single fibre path, which is repeated all over the circumference. For asymmetric structures, a whole set of different fibre paths is needed to cover the part totally. Two consecutive paths, which have only a small initial shift, fast diverge if they encounter areas of the part that are not identical. Filament winding such parts requires therefore the generation of a large number of individual fibre paths, which, when combined, cover the surface of the mandrel completely.

The different geodesical fibre trajectories which are possible on the part are investigated. Patterns are selected which approximate the ideal orientations. Paths where fibre bridging are excluded. In order to get a uniform coverage, individual winding paths are selected within these winding patterns which remain as parallel to each other as possible. If there remain parts uncovered, individual additional fibre paths are calculated for these parts.

The laminate lay-up in every point of the finite element mesh is then determined. Stress calculations are performed on the composite part to check if all of the requirements of

strength and stiffness are met. The lay-up is then adapted until strength and stiffness are achieved to permit the structure to operate safely. In zones where winding is not possible in the loaded directions, f.e. in locally concave areas, reinforcements are added before or after winding.

3 PRODUCTION OF FILAMENT WOUND PARTS

At the K.U.Leuven two filament winding units have been developed : a numerically controlled two-axis machine and a robotic filament winding unit.

3.1 Two axes filament winding machine A low cost filament winding machine with two axes has been developed to wind axisymmetrical parts. The first axis of this machine is the mandrel drive, the second axis is an oscillating arm on which the payout eye is mounted [2]. The payout eye describes a circular path in a vertical plane parallel to the mandrel axis. The length of the oscillating arm can be adjusted in functions of the dimensions of the mandrel. The inertia of the winding arm is very small compared to the inertia of the carriage in a conventional translational filament winding machine, so that higher winding speeds can be obtained. The velocities of both axes are controlled in such a way that even for complex axisymmetrical parts a constant winding speed is obtained.

3.2 Robotic filament winding machine To be able to wind complex non-axisymmetric shapes, a filament winding machine with more degrees of freedom is needed. Instead of using an expensive filament winding machine, a cheaper industrial articulated PUMA-762 robot from Unimation is used.

Due to the kinematic construction of the robot the inertia of the fibre delivery system is less than the inertia of the delivery system of a conventional cartesian filament winder, so that a higher winding speed is possible. The accuracy of an articulated robot is however less than the accuracy of a cartesian winder. The accuracy can be ameliorated by the use of special calibration techniques. This robot can also be used to load or unload the mandrel and for quality control.

The filament winding cell consists of a fibre feeding unit (tension control unit and impregnation bath), the PUMA-762 robot, on which the payout eye is mounted, and a mandrel support unit with the mandrel drive (Fig. 1). The robot has six degrees of

Figure 1: Filament Winding Cell

freedom, and is off-line programmable in the VAL-II language.

The payout eye (Fig. 2) is suited to wind unidirectional tapes by the addition of a supplementary rotation round the fibre feeding axis. If tapes are used, the orientation of the tape at the exit point of the payout eye becomes important : if the orientation of the tape in the payout eye differs from the orientation in the contact point on the mandrel, the tape can slip or contract inside the payout eye. During the winding process the tape twists round its own length axis. When this twisting becomes too large, the tape can fold together, causing a void and thus a weak spot in the part. This is also avoided by the use of an appropriate strategy for the motion of the payout eye. The payout eye consists of several proportional rotatable disks, at which rolls are connected. Fibre twisting can be stored temporarily in between these rolls, and are released at the end of a fibre path behind pin rings, which are mounted at the end of the part and cut away after curing.

The robotic filament winding machine is controlled by an external PC/AT. This PC sends at constant time intervals motion commands to the PUMA-robot, the mandrel drive and the payout eye rotation.

Figure 2: Payout eye

3.3 Calculation of the Robot Path Filament winding of complex shapes has commonly been performed with the "teach-in" method [3]. The operator continuously leads the payout eye through the winding process, teaching it how to lay the fibre along the desired path, and records the position of the winding machine at regular time intervals. With this method, instantly a collision-free control program is generated with a direct visual control of mandrel coverage. The teaching operation is however very time-consuming and occupies the machine for a long unproductive time. The accuracy of fibre placement is however very low.

It is far more interesting to compute the control data of the machine in advance and create an off-line control program. The work of the operator is reduced to a minimum, and the machine is freed for production runs only. The accuracy of fibre placement will increase. Every possible collision between the robot and the mandrel and the winding environment will have to be predicted and prevented.

The data of the selected fibre paths are used to calculate the position of the robot and both external axes. But first the sequence in which the fibre paths will have to be wound is calculated. A desired sequence of fibre paths, inputted by the user, is adapted in such a way that the end point of the last path and the starting point of the next path are on the same pin ring, and that there is as less material as possible on these pin rings.

3.4 Position of the payout eye The robotic filament winding unit has in total 8 degrees of freedom. It is therefore a redundant system, since only 6 degrees of freedom are needed to determine the position and rotation of the payout eye. In order to reduce the system to a determined system, only 4 degrees of freedom of the robot are used : 3 translations of the robot wrist and the rotation of the robot wrist around the vertical axis.

During winding the exit point of the payout eye has to be on the tangent to the fibre path in the contact point on the mandrel. The fibre may not slip between the rolls at the exit point of the payout eye. No transverse force, caused by the difference between the orientation of the fibre in the contact point on the mandrel and in the payout eye, is therefore allowed. This condition is a.o. fulfilled when the direction of the tape is the same in the payout eye as in the contact point on the mandrel.

Based on the data of the fibre path an ideal robot position is calculated. The exit point of the payout eye is then at a constant distance from the contact point on the mandrel. The orientation of the payout eye is the same as the orientation of the fibre in the contact point on the mandrel. The mandrel is then rotated in such a way that the tangent to the fibre path becomes horizontal. The rotation axis in the payout eye aligns the tape in the contact point with the tape in the payout eye.

Due to various possible collisions, this solution can not always be used. If the part has locally concave parts, collisions can occur between mandrel and both payout eye and robot wrist. Both payout eye and robot can collide with the supports of the filament winding machine. It is also possible that the requested position lays outside the working area of the robot.

The robot path is constructed in several consecutive steps :

1. The robot path consists of two parts : a starting motion, which links the current fibre path to the previous fibre path, and the normal motion. The motion of the fibre round the pin rings is first defined, and ideal robot positions for both the starting motion and the normal motion are calculated. In this step the robot and the rotation of the mandrel are not yet taken into account : the positions are calculated relatively to the mandrel.
2. Calculation of the maximum distance between the contact point on the mandrel and the exit point of the payout eye. This distance is limited when the tangent

to the fibre path has an intersection with another part of the mandrel or with the supports of the filament winding machine. If the proposed distance is less than the allowed distance, a new position for the payout eye is calculated.

3. Collisions between the mandrel and the payout eye are detected. If the distance between the axis of the payout eye and the surface is smaller than the radius of the payout eye, collision occurs. An alternative position is then sought by changing the orientation of the payout eye or by changing the distance between the contact point and the payout eye. The new positions are connected by a smooth collision free path.
4. The rotation of the mandrel drive and the position of the robot wrist are calculated, so that the fibre in the payout eye becomes horizontal. Collisions between robot wrist and the mandrel or machine supports can occur, or the proposed position can be outside the working area of the robot. If the proposed position is not possible, a corrective action is taken by changing the rotation of the robot wrist round the vertical axis, or the rotation of the external axis, or the distance between the contact point on the mandrel and the exit point of the payout eye. The new positions are connected by a smooth path, and the previous step is repeated for the adapted points.
5. The rotation in the payout eye is calculated so that the tape does not slip inside the payout eye. During winding round the pin rings, the fibre twisting that are stored in the payout eye are released and future fibre twisting foreseen.

4 ROBOTIC ULTRASONIC C-SCAN

The PUMA robot, which is used to wind the composite part is also used to test the wound part. An ultrasonic sensor (sender and receiver) is mounted on the robot wrist. While moving this sensor at a constant distance perpendicular over the surface, defects in the composite part can be detected. A constant distance is achieved by making continuously contact between the surface and the housing of the sensor, that is mounted on the robot wrist. A spring, which is mounted in between the robot wrist and the housing of the sensor compensates the tracking error of the robot. A waterjet is the coupling medium. The robot is controlled out from the PC, that controls the filament winding process.

Figure 3: Scanning Cell

The geometrical data, which are stored in the CAD-system and in the IGES-file, are used to generate a mesh of points on the surface. The end points of the robot tool, that correspond to these mesh points, are then calculated and downloaded from the VAX-computer to the PC. During the scanning process, a supplementary interpolation is performed between the mesh points to obtain the desired scanning accuracy. The ultrasonic measuring data are stored in the memory of the PC and sent back to the VAX-computer, where an image analysis is performed on a workstation.

5 CONCLUSIONS

A robotic filament winding unit has been constructed, consisting of a robot with 6 degrees of freedom and 2 external axes : the mandrel drive and a rotation inside the payout eye. This unit enables filament winding with tapes.

A computer-integrated method has been developed to design and produce asymmetric filament wound parts, like T-connections. Out from a drawing in a CAD-system, geodesic paths are calculated. These paths are then selected in such a way that a

uniformly covered and strong part is obtained. The locations of the robot and the angular positions of the external axes are computed, so that there occur no collisions. The robot program is then downloaded to the PC which controls the filament winding process. After filament winding, the robot can test the part for defects using the ultrasonic C-scan method, using almost the same software.

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